

Discipline and Classroom Management

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Abstract

Students are humans with real needs and aspirations. If their needs are not taken into account, significant improvement is unlikely. The purpose of this study is to demonstrate the positive effects discipline rules can have when they are used by teachers in the learning environment. Discipline impacts the learning process by creating a stress-free environment, improves planning through observation, and helps teachers manage the class easier. There are also negative effects in the learning environment if discipline rules are not implemented by teachers. Another important issue is classroom management. Some key points in order to have successful classroom management in every school are: understanding your students, setting effective limits, keeping the schedule, engaging students, etc. Also, in this study, the behaviors of the teachers will be analyzed and in addition the methods they should use in order to maintain a successful learning environment. The focus of this research are on the students of the 10th and 12th grades of “Zihni Magani high school in Peqin. Part of the study are also all teachers in that high school including English and other teachers of foreign languages.

Keywords: Discipline Rules, Classroom Management, Learning Environment, Teachers

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1. Introduction

Nowadays, we know more about teaching than we have ever had before. This happens because teaching in our days has advanced a lot into the computer and television age and we get new information each day. Even for teachers, things have changed a lot and they are facing new methods or ways of teaching. Their job is to guide and train students to know how to continue the journey of learning alone but in a very capable way. While doing so, teachers have to be very careful in managing the classroom, because classroom management affects student's ability to learn and, what is more important, teachers' ability to teach.

Classroom management is one of the most important aspects of teaching. A very important step of teaching is how to build the right 'architecture' through which we as teachers are going to give lessons. The way we teach, job strategies with students, and the implementation of personal knowledge in function to class is an enormous help for both sides, even for us as teachers, even for those whom we teach (students). It is very important for teachers to have a kind of natural instinct while presenting the lesson. According to Arons (2010), classroom management is a complex set of skills that includes more than being able to influence and control students' behavior. Classroom management is primarily about discipline. Discipline is a kind of action to regulate student behaviors. It refers to some rules or strategies which are applied in school to manage student behavior. Somehow students have to obey some rules or standards of behavior in order to maintain a successful learning environment in school. If students are not disciplined, then they will be able to be free and plan whatever they wish. This means bunking the classes. That is why discipline in the classroom is really important, to avoid students breaking the rules.

1.2 Theoretical Framework

Many teachers admit that managing a class and trying to maintain students' discipline is really tough. They have to deal with a lot of difficulties during classes. According to the research made at the "Zihni Magani" high school in Peqin, most of the teachers there admit that discipline rules are difficult to be followed by their students. This brings some problems while managing the class. Those students, who have problems following discipline rules, also distract other students and create an unpleasant learning environment.

The purpose of this study is to find out the reasons why students who have problems with discipline rules behave in such a way and what teachers can do or what methods they can use to avoid these

behaviors and maintain a successful learning environment. The focus will be applied to the students of the 10th and 12th grades of “Zihni Magani” high school in Peqin.

2. Literature review

2.1 Classroom management and its significance

“Self-respect, respect others, respect learning, and respect property” (Harry Wong), and that means successful classroom management. If respect exists, classroom management functions. Classroom management is a term used by teachers to describe the process of teaching a class without facing problems like noisy students or undisciplined ones. It can be considered a magical element that permits teachers to succeed or even ‘survive’ in a class. For some teachers, it might be difficult to control the class and to have all the student’s attention (it does not mean that this experience cannot be gained through the passing of the years), while for others it is like a gift because they have the ability to control the class or to easily assume their authority role. According to Elizabeth Mulvahill (2018), - “Classroom management refers to the wide variety of skills and techniques that teachers use to ensure that their classroom runs smoothly, without disruptive behavior from students. Classroom management and effective instruction are the keys to ensuring students’ success in learning. To manage a class means to plan, to organize procedures and recourses, to monitor student’s progress, to minimize disruption and also discipline problems.” If teachers go to school unprepared, they will lose control of the class, and if they lose it, they will never have successful classroom management. Teachers should have a lot of materials before entering the class and also a plan B, in order not to create pauses during lessons. If these pauses happen, students will lose their attention, and classroom management will not function. Also, if teachers work really hard, there are some students who do not obey and create difficulties in the learning environment. It causes problems to other students too because they lose their attention, so not everything depends on teachers, but also on students’ efforts to get involved in the class. As mentioned above “unpleasant memories “affect students.

2.2 Successful classroom management and discipline/teaching self-control and responsibility

According to Tom V Savage and Marsha K. Savage, - “Management refers to the ability teachers have to create a classroom environment where success is possible. It refers to how the order is maintained in the classroom, while discipline is about stopping misbehavior really quickly and helping students learn to accept responsibilities for their own actions. When bringing order to

complex classrooms, teachers have to arrange a physical environment, organize lessons with a logical flow, motivate students to reach their goals, and the most important thing establish their own authority.” (Sage, 2009) It is really important to stress that classroom management is not a discipline; they differ in terms and techniques. Discipline plans have rules while classroom management plans have procedures, which means that classroom management is a method or process for getting things done.

One important aspect of classroom management is self-control. Learning self-control, for students, means being allowed to make your own choices and reflect on the consequences of the choices you made. And for teachers is important to treat equally all students, understand their needs, and avoid shouting at them. Literature suggests that it is very important for students to start learning about obligations, duties, and consequences from a young age. These qualities will help students become better constructive members of society. First of all, teachers should talk to students about responsibility and should be clear with their intentions and what they are trying to achieve by teaching it to the students. This will make it easier for everyone to follow their obligations. Secondly, they should help students with their tasks. Rather than getting angry when students do something wrong, teachers need to be patient and give them positive feedback in order to do it right next time and help them as much as they can. Another important thing to do as a teacher in order to teach responsibility to students is to establish consequences. If students fail to execute a certain task or are not following the procedures, let them know they will miss out on the playtime. On the other hand, if they have completed all the tasks, praise them for doing it, it is not necessary to reward them with material things (Gonzalez, 2020).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Sampling and Procedure

In this study, 12 teachers and 60 students participated in total. 29 of them are in 10th grade and 31 others are in 12th grade. They were considered as the appropriate group level of English B2. Students attended English classes 4 times a week throughout the year. The main reason for this study is to know how classroom management and discipline rules function in high school. This research was conducted at “Zihni Magani “high- school in Peqin. Students were between 16-18 years old. There were 18 female and 11 male students in the 10th grade and 22 female and 9

male students in the 12th grade. The mother tongue of students was Albanian and the level of English was upper-intermediate.

3.2. Measurement tool

For the purpose of this study, qualitative questionnaires have been used. The questionnaires were given to the students of both classes, and to all teachers at school in order to complete them and give their sincere answers, of course without revealing their names. There were two questionnaires, one for students of 10th & 12th in “Zihni Magani “high school and another 25 for all of their teachers. The participants were chosen randomly, because they may give better and more reliable information for the survey. Only teachers knew before about the observation and questionnaires, but not the questions on them.

3. RESULTS

The questionnaires were completed by students of 10th and 12th grades and 12 teachers of all subjects, not only those of English language. The age of the students in the survey was 16 and 18 years old. The survey was made of 12 questions. 6 questions were directed to teachers and 6 others to students and the purpose of the survey was to find out how classroom management and discipline rules function in high school.

Creating successful learning environment graphic

Student's difficulties to follow discipline rules

According to the student's and teachers' responses and the purpose of the study, resulted that most of the students have difficulties in following discipline rules. The majority of teachers who answered the questionnaire admit that discipline rules are very difficult to be followed by their students and because of this they have problems managing the class. Most of them confirm

the difficulties students have when following these rules, but there was also a small number of teachers who admit that students cope pretty well with them and the rules they have decided.

Based on teachers' experience in their classrooms, they declare that students are able to think critically about discipline rules even though some of them refuse to respect them. This problem mostly happens with 12th-grade students, where for 22 of them is very difficult to follow discipline rules. So, students who have these difficulties also have a negative effect on other classmates.

Teachers' opinions about using different methods to create a better learning environment had a positive effect. They state that by using those methods, things changed a lot in their classrooms and students started to cope with them and follow their rules and directions. Most importantly when students are exposed to activities, it means they interact more with other classmates, and by interacting they have the possibility to stay focused on the goals teachers have to decide in order to make it easier for them to manage the class. Teachers also assume that managing a class needs a lot of effort and also it does not only depend on their performance as teachers, but also on the ability of students to show them.

According to students' responses, they admit that it is very difficult for most of them to follow discipline rules. They state that this happens because of teachers' lack of attention or even because of problems they have at home.

4. Conclusion

According to the results of the survey, the importance of discipline rules is emphasized in the learning environment. By analyzing the data of this survey, it can be concluded that teachers need to be good "managers".

The Research Finding Based on the data analysis, can be listed as the followings:

- Deciding discipline rules together with students makes class a better learning environment;
- Staying close to students, asking what problems do they have, include them in different class activities, can make them better students and you as a teacher a better classroom manager;
- Talking with students is always effective and will make them cope with teachers;
- A successful classroom management means a successful teacher-student relationship.

5. Recommendations

According to the conclusions drawn from the research when reading and analyzing different information in the literature section and based on the data gathered through the questionnaire on teachers and students about the research questions raised in the introduction, some recommendations to be considered for teachers are as the following:

- It is important for every teacher to know how to decide discipline rules in the learning environment so they won't affect negatively their students.
- It is crucial for teachers to decide on these rules with their students, by asking for their opinion and feedback. In this way, teachers will create a more positive classroom environment, and this will allow them to dedicate more time to teaching, rather than warning students every moment. This makes students lose interest in the subject.
- It is very important for teachers to understand students' social, emotional, and cultural backgrounds. This category of teachers can be considered better classroom managers.
- Teachers should be able to manage the physical environment. They must see every student, manage traffic flow during transitions, and strategically group students.

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